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Juliana Peiró Pérez

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Article

Being as Absolute *Beginning*: Metaphysical Considerations Regarding the Gifted Character of Being *Ex Nihilo*

Juliana Peiró Pérez ^{1,2} ¹ Hápax. Action Science Institute, Mexico City 14000, Mexico; juliana.peiro@hapax.ac; Tel.: +52-77720-90446² Facultad de Filosofía y Ciencias Religiosas, Instituto Teológico Digital, Mexico City 14000, Mexico; juliana.peiro@unir.net

Abstract: The metaphysical crisis that Western thought is going through—whose main sign is nihilism—can be overcome through an understanding of the finite being that, precisely understood as *ex nihilo*, excludes nothingness from itself. This paper analyzes the notion of being *ex nihilo* and its real dynamism through the contributions provided by the metaphysics of the gift. The origin of being *ex nihilo* as *donatio essendi* is addressed first; we then move on to a reflection of finite being as given and absolute beginning. In this paper, I will aim to show that (§1) the notion of *donatio essendi* is a radical way of conceiving being as an absolute novelty that safeguards God's freedom while securing the proper novelty of created being, (§2) then illustrate how created being is an absolute gift wholly dependent on the divine being, especially if the created being is a person, and (§3) finally, explain how these theses are compatible with an existential interpretation of the *actus essendi* according to the first principle of metaphysics, i.e., being as noncontradiction.

Keywords: gifted character; absolute beginning; *donatio essendi*; metaphysics of the gift; being *ex nihilo*

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1. Introduction

It has been evident for several decades that Western metaphysical thought is immersed in a cultural crisis that manifests as grave ethical, political, economic and ecological challenges. Even if determining the causes that have taken us to this situation is not an easy task, for the purposes of this paper, it may suffice to point out that the ethical/moral relativism that accompanies every cultural crisis is nothing more than a reflection of a deeper one, anthropological and metaphysical in nature.¹

Regarding the current crisis of metaphysics and the subsequent loss of sense in the question about truth and being that constitutes reality, one of its main causes can be seen, in my view, in the crisis of rationality denounced by Husserl in the 1930s. The father of phenomenology warned, then, about the peculiar dangers arising from encircling what is rational to the remnant of what positive science understands as its object and method² in such a way that everything overcoming this limit falls in the abyss of the irrational.³ Such has been the drift from what appeared then to be a menace (*The Crisis*, Husserl 1976, pp. 11–12) endangering the very pillars of modern society, ultimately resolved, for a good portion of contemporary philosophy, in the end of metaphysics and the inevitable sinking into a lack of meaning, devastating at every level.

We can thus see that metaphysical decline is a consequence—among other reasons—of a gnoseological self-absorption that signals a suffocating subjectivism that renders us incapable of the mere possibility of knowledge itself, as it truncates the aspiration for truth beyond opinion in its very beginning. This is the proper horizon of the road towards Heidegger's "Zerstörung der Metaphysik" in *Being and Time* (Heidegger 1927, sct. 6) knowledge and truth, radical hermeneutics and transhumanism.⁴ Such a process within the debates of first philosophy can only culminate in so-called metaphysical nihilism (Zubiri 1996, pp. 56–57), the final stage of the metaphysical crisis that leads to our current society,

while every human being is headed towards despair as an unequivocal sign of an existence bereft of meaning (Vargas 2020, pp. 33–82).

A metaphysics of being as an act, however, such as the one laid forth by Aristotle and Saint Thomas,⁵ can rightfully hold that the question about the kind of being that originates and sustains reality is not one that confronts extramental existence with its opposite, that is, nothingness, as a philosophy of being, real being, even if *ex nihilo*—and because it is *ex nihilo*—lacks an absolute contradiction. In this meaning—the one referred to by Leibniz first and then by Heidegger when undertaking the question “Why is there something rather than nothing?”—real or proper being is not under consideration, but rather its intelligible conception, which is not real but ideal. Only an ideal being can be opposed to nothingness as its contrary, because only mental being, as thought, can be conceived as given, i.e., in a “position” that allows for the possibility of something previous. Real being—the *actus essendi*—however, cannot be opposed precisely because it is not thought, or supposed. Therefore, when dealing with the question about the being that sustains reality, we can never posit a real opposition, only a distinction, as these acts are not in reality opposite but diverse (Peiró 2014).

Alejandro Llano and Fernando Inciarte put forth the question: “Is a Metaphysics possible, after the end of metaphysics?” (Inciarte and Llano 2007, p. 15); my aim in this paper is an attempt to begin this investigation, after the premise that metaphysics can find a possible way to overcome contemporary nihilism through an understanding of finite being that, as being *ex nihilo*, excludes nothingness from itself.⁶ To accomplish this undertaking, I focus on being *ex nihilo* and its own character through the metaphysics of the gift.⁷ First, I investigate the origin of being *ex nihilo* in terms of a donation essence, turning later to the study on finite being as giftedness and absolute beginning. Approaching these notions through the metaphysics of the gift, I contend, will allow us to overcome postmodern skepticism and relativism, the parting point of metaphysic nihilism. In my view, this overcoming is possible by a strong acknowledgment of human rationality that recognizes the true nature of being, that is, its own intelligibility and its incompatibility with any sort of univocity, equivocation, ambiguity or constitutive frailty.

2. The Value of the Thomistic *Donation Essendi* in the Question about Being

As Husserl claimed in a posthumous manuscript: “An autonomous philosophy, such as Aristotelianism was and as what remains a continuous demand, necessarily brings us to teleology, and a theological philosophy, as a non-confessional road towards God.”⁸ According to this claim, the question of being takes us necessarily to the question about its Origin, one that is pure actuality and whose original quality consists in not being able to be thought of in a way that is previous to its realization (Inciarte and Llano 2007, pp. 24, 349). It is therefore the radical metaphysical question, the question about the being of the world, effectively, the question about which activity sustains it and ultimately propels us towards the Absolute as Origin. If any being were questioned, it would answer with its finitude, insofar as things exist only partially and in a particular way; hence, they are not their being: their existence does not refer to themselves nor does it exist in itself, theirs is not a consummate and completed existence. Rather, their own lacking becomes a claim towards their Origin. That is why metaphysics cannot relinquish natural theology, as doing so would make it unable to investigate the root of its own subject: the being of the universe as an act of being *ex nihilo*.⁹

We know Aquinas holds several times that God’s creating freedom is absolute (Thomas de Aquino 2001, *De Pot.*, q.3, a. 15, sol.). In this fashion, he turns to the formal, necessary deduction or derivation of pagan Neoplatonism, which he knew and challenged, e.g., Avicenna’s metaphysics (Thomas de Aquino 2005a, *In Sent.*, II, d. 18, q. 2, a. 2, sol.). According to Aquinas, God creates whatever he wills, in whatever fashion and for whatever reason he wills, but, and this nuance is important, not according to an arbitrary will but rather a loving and wise intent: “As the creature proceeds from God in diversity of nature,

God is outside the order of the whole creation (. . .) for He does not produce the creature by necessity of His nature, but by His intellect and will.”¹⁰

According to creation, being is not produced as an idea, nor is created being the blind and necessary effect of the divine cause. That is why, in order to make way for divine freedom, intrinsic to the originating act, we must allow for the metaphysical gap that opens our view to an action beyond that which is necessarily established by the necessity and contingency of the natural order of causes and productions. Aquinas is one of the first thinkers to undertake this metaphysical fracture through a comparative analysis between creation. The key concept is the recognition that creatures are endowed with an act of being that originates by means of an action that is the origin of all they are. Truthfully, in several passages, he mentions that previous thinkers did not take up the idea of creation because they never considered the act of being. For Aquinas, considering *esse* as the act of existence is necessary to understand reality as created—an idea that is intelligible independently from Trinitarian theology and even God’s existence. However, Trinitarian theology is what allows him to reach the deeper meaning of creation, all the way up to the conclusion that an unequivocal free notion of creation requires an idea of beginning that goes beyond the concept of cause, producer or artisan: the notion of person. This, in turn, drives him to consider creative action through the sieve of the personal action par excellence: amorous donation.¹¹

This comparative analysis allows Aquinas to explain creation as donation, in an analogous way, with the divine processions ad intra: creation as *donation essendi*.¹² The clearest passage in this regard can be found in his Commentary on the Gospel of John, wherein he explicitly holds that: “But God acts in all things from within, because he acts by creating. Now to create is to give existence (*esse*) to the thing created. So, since *esse* is innermost in each thing, God, who by acting gives *esse* acts in things from within.”¹³

As the quintessential free action, creation has an unblemished rational and voluntary character that encourages an interpretation as a personal act of love. The reason is that creative freedom, while showing that nothing interlopes between the divine will and the creature (there is no third action or receptive subject) (Thomas de Aquino 2001, *De Pot.*, q. 3, a. 3, sol.), identifies the creative act with an act of generosity, namely the gifting of being. This is especially noticeable when considering the radical novelty that radical being *ex nihilo* introduces in the scheme of free creation: only a personal understanding of creation can explore the whole scope of divine freedom introduced by creation, of which human freedom is an image (González 2013, p. 49). Only through this view can the essence of creation transcend its speculative center, release all of logical–formal or dialectical necessity (Pangallo 1991, p. 86) and show its true character as a giving, amorous and effusive act.¹⁴

It is true, however, that Aquinas does not always distinguish between giving, causing and producing when talking about creation.¹⁵ The reason for this apparent ambiguity is, in my view, that the three terms, in their common use regarding the created order, seem to perfectly adjust with an action proper to the uncreated being. On the whole, however, Thomistic metaphysics establishes a hierarchical order among them, for, as Falgueras points out, even if “giving”, “causing” and “producing” are used as synonyms many times, they signify quite different actions, and out of those three, the specific nature of creating finds its best expression in the idea of an absolute or transcendental gift (Falgueras 1997, pp. 83–84).

This is the reason why the best explanation for *creatio active sumpta* is not one that points out the proper notes of physical causation or production, but rather one that acknowledges that the core of creation is gratuity and freedom. Thus, we should conceive creation as a real form of communication, one that is donative, real and pure: creation is absolute donation. In the first place, because the radical novelty of creative being is only manifest when we understand the donative character of being *ex nihilo*. Moreover, only from the notion of *donatio essendi* can safeguard divine freedom: when God creates, he donates without becoming the passive subject of an ad extra relation. We can thus affirm, as a direct corollary, the absolute gratuity of creation, which becomes absolute benefit. The way created being depends on its creator is only as a gift. Being created means being received

as gift, not caused or produced; being created is being given as granted. In this fashion, it is a being from another and for another (especially in the case of rational, free beings); in other words, being dependent towards another.

As *donatio essendi* par excellence, the philosophy of being conceives of reality as the communication of absolute giftedness that, unlike other explanatory frameworks, dismantles the scheme of ontological monism (which corresponds to univocal predication) and brings us to an open predication grounded on the exclusion of an idea of the “totality of the real”. A metaphysics such as this follows the real distinction between *esse* and *essential*. In ontological terms, creation means a leap into reality itself, a sort of transcendental discontinuity which opens up the space of radical innovation that is the world as the donation of being *ex nihilo*. The theoretical advantage of such a reading of the original act of existence lays in the mentioned discontinuity between originating and originated reality, safekeeping the plenitude of divine freedom as well as the novelty of being (See Haya 1997, op. cit., p. 206; also Verdú 2019, p. 127). From this stage, we can rationalize the coexistence of two real orders, both absolutely diverse and transcendently linked: the uncreated and the created order.

By focusing our attention in the absolutely free nature of being *ex nihilo*, we can also conceptualize the radical innovation of the *donatio essendi* in its own terms, necessary to account for personal created being, as every person is a surge when seen from the rest of reality. In what follows, I try to show how being *ex nihilo* relates to what F. Haya has called metaphysics of the gift (Haya 1997, p. 320), with the aim of describing created being *ex nihilo* as an absolute *acceptio esse*, as well as characterizing the donative nature of personal beings, which are even more radically defined as being *ex Deo* than by being *ex nihilo* (Haya 1997, p. 206).

3. The Donated Nature of Being *Ex Nihilo* as Absolute *Acceptio Esse* and Personal Being as Being *Ex Deo*

Even if the daily notion of gift is not perfectly applicable to creation, active and passively considered, we can employ it through the idea of *donatio essendi* from a transcendental point of view.

“The phenomenology of the pure gift -Haya writes- describes the manifestation of a reality that is not contained in its precedent conditions insofar as it has none. An absolute gift is no gift if it is contained in the giver, in such a fashion that its being consists only in its deployment or being made explicit. In turn, absolute giving, as an action, is essentially free and gratuitous, in the sense that no necessity constricts either the giver or the giving itself, and the giver is only one insofar as we consider the act of giving itself.” (Haya 1997, op. cit., p. 324)

In these lines, we find the thesis that giving involves from a free being, so that such an action pertains to what is most peculiar in the giver: its intimacy. A gift is so because it is donated, so that donation can be construed as the character of personal beings, as their radical way of existence according to their being a gifted act, which implies gratuity, that is, no less than an unprecedented giving (González 2013, p. 45).

In order for a donation to be pure, there must be a giver and a gift that is absolute. What is specific about giving, in turn, as absolute benefit, is absolute regarding the action of giving, in such a way that there is no way to hold that there is a giver or an act of giving without the gift, as an absolute donation involves no necessity. The act of giving implies freedom; on the other hand, if an absolute donation needs no receptor of the gift, then giving is an immanent action, for there is no term that sets limits upon it, nor is its goal outside of giving. This is perfectly compatible with the ratio creations, as giving (*donare esse, in Aquinas's terms*) is creating. What is given is precisely being, that is to say, everything, or rather, the gift itself, which is a giver that donates itself. It is an act that requires no alterity, because *ex nihilo* implies absolute inexistence and therefore the complete absence of an awaiting receptacle (González 2013, p. 49). In other words: if *donatio pura* is creation, it cannot have any requirements, not even someone who receives it.

That is why the perspective of a metaphysics of the gift is capable of giving meaning to the absolute reception of being, a new radical significance that can hold an answer to the inevitable problem of the passivity of being that accompanies the idea of *acceptio esse*. In order to correctly gauge the notion of being *ex nihilo* as given, the only possible way goes through thinking it as radical benefit, for, again, there cannot be a receptacle, and the idea that what is received is divine in any way is also inadmissible (because what is received is precisely what is *ex nihilo*).

The absolute relativity of being *ex nihilo* implies no passivity, even and as a gift, and even less so with regards to free beings: giving is not self-referential and an absolute donation is not a passive receptor (González 2013, p. 47). We know, however, that, for Aquinas, creation, from the viewpoint of the creature, is an absolute *acceptio esse* (Thomas de Aquino 2005a, *In Sent.* II, d. 1, q. 1, a. 2, ad 2). This cannot mean, at any rate, that the creature's essence, as really distinct from being, acts as a receptor of any kind. On the contrary, according to Aquinas, the essence is ontologically posterior and dependent on being and cocreated with it, so that it cannot contain it: what is perfect always contains what is imperfect. The idea of creation as absolute reception must then signal to a different way of reception: a reception without a previous receiver. This is what makes it "absolute"; what is created is entirely the receiver, or rather, the receiver is the gifted existence.

Only when thought of as absolute benefit can being *ex nihilo* be understood as gifted being. This is because absolute donation relates to absolute receiving, that is, radical benefit or radical gain, which does not imply any sort of necessity or demand in gifting on behalf of what is gifted. As M. J. Soto explains: "Creating, as God's proper act, is properly giving being, but not the being of the Creator but rather the being of what is created." (Soto-Bruna 2002, p. 147). Being *ex nihilo* consists in this benefit on the part of what is gifted; even more so, it identifies with it, as its being is being-given. This is what we mean by being *ex nihilo* as absolute benefit, in such a way that the *donatio essendi* adds nothing to God.¹⁶

"Giving is more than just diffusion", as Gonzalez says, for it excludes any sort of passivity. The activity of a donated being is centered in its dependency and subordination. The absolute correlate of giving, for its part, is not receiving but rather accepting; this is the activity of being *ex nihilo* in its deepest dimension as revealed by a metaphysics of the gift, for the superior active character of being given consists in its acceptance of being relative, or in other words, its being obedient regarding the being on whom it depends and it is subordinated to. How should we understand the activity of those beings without conscience of their gifted being? The question is not exempt from difficulties; as a provisional answer, I should like to point out the convenience of recognizing, as Polo does, that there are different ways of being a creature, according to the intensity of donated being (Polo 2016, p. 90).

Indeed, according to Polo, we can pursue two distinct senses of creation: one is the universe, or cosmic being, while the other is the person, the personal act of being. For creatures, being is not always the same. The high point of Polo's proposal (which, in my view is coherent with Aquinas, i.e., that beings are distinct according to their differing acts of being, which order them towards the origin) (See Kerr 2019). is that it does not accommodate the differences between creatures in a gradual scale, from less to more perfect (as some Thomists suggest (Fabro 2009, p. 137), from a lesser to a more intense perfection, as Thomism does; it is, rather, a real distinction that qualifies the differing existential character of the acts of being. It is a proposal that accepts a plurality from the Origin as corresponding to a plural meaning of creation, for the intensity of dependence is directly proportional to the distinction of created beings (Polo 1993, p. 57).

From the previous lines, we can infer that the gifted character of being *ex nihilo* as absolute *acceptio esse* implies that, if being is an amorous and absolute donation, what the *ad extra* communication of divine being adds is a phenomenology of the gift that, as what is given, as radical gain, is something purely and absolutely relative to the action of giving. Moreover, a complete understanding of being *ex nihilo* as absolute receiving clarifies how the personal act of being is, in the end, a giving of oneself, beyond being given. Thinking about being necessitates its understanding as a giving existence. Hence, Haya writes, from

the point of view of the gift, we have a full manifestation of the gifted character of being *ex nihilo*: it is not something previously given or contained—this would belong to what is included in the essence—but rather to act itself towards its intensification.¹⁷

Metaphysically understood, creation *qua donatio essendi* consists in the communication of relative actuality. To create means to grant the giving: not giving gifts but forming being, and not on something that is previous to being, but being that does not possess its own being, as it exists *ex nihilo*. In the case of created being, being is also donating, but donating gifts, not the giving itself, which only belongs to the Original giver. This does not mean that personal beings, as absolute gifts, cannot give their own giving, or that the donated being is incapable of giving itself to other personal beings through its essence, which is cocreated along their personal existence; on the contrary, as a giving reality, the subsistent personal being implies its own capacity of giving without mediators or deviations. Its intensity as a donating being means that personal being is even more *ex Deo* than *ex nihilo*: it is an absolute gift. A personal being achieves its own perfection in its giving itself: it acts then not only at an essential level but in what is proper of its own *actus essendi*: as destination (Haya 1997, p. 314). Otherwise, the donating nature of personal being would end up truncated.

From the point of view of the metaphysics of the gift, the existence of the universe can be understood as something that is radically initiated, and in this sense, different from the Original being while totally dependent upon it. Through the notions of gifted being and to the absolute gift, we may develop a comprehension of the *ad extra* communication of divine being, both in its diffusive nature, as *donatio essendi*, and in its return, for the nature of the gifted being implies that its plenitude as gift-being is more in the return to the Giver than in itself. In this sense, we can conclude that the donating action of being to the gifted being is a real communication, because it is real and absolute, and therefore free. When God created, He gives without construing a real *ad extra* relation (Pérez-Guerrero 1996, p. 159). In turn, if the gifted character of being *ex nihilo* consists in its dependence, the absolute gifted nature of the personal being, being *ex Deo*, consists in its own destination and radical giving of itself to the Origin.

4. From Absolute Beginning to Absolute Dependence: The Metaphysical Dynamic of the Gifted Act of Being (*Acceptio Esse*)

In the previous section, we described the essential attributes of being *ex nihilo* and being *ex Deo* as an absolute gift from the perspective of the metaphysics of the gift. This analysis allows for a better understanding of the nature of givenness, one that implies that the plenitude of the given-being is more in returning its gift to the Given than within himself. In order to complement this analysis of the *donatio essendi* and what it entails as a donated being *ex nihilo*, I now turn to the study of the way in which the donated character becomes manifest in the dynamics of reality, namely, the way in which the act of being, as absolute beginning, is essentially a dependence. I show how, through the notion of gifted being, reality, insofar as it is *ex nihilo*, is recognized as beginning and absolute growth (Haya 1997, p. 323).

We have noted that, for Thomas Aquinas, being is not a *factum* or the sameness of the mental object but a first act or principle. A metaphysics that holds up to this will not conceive being as data, an object or a static identity, not even as an activity that merely opposes nothingness by “being”, as if it could just exist even while not fully realizing its being; being is the metaphysical sense of activity donated on a transcendental level (Polo 2015b, p. 55). Hence, the most adequate expression of the gifted character of being *ex nihilo* is absolute beginning and with no continuation: absolute given being. This modality of activity of things, as inseparable from *donatio essendi*, can be properly named inchoated activity, or in other words, an activity that (like sunrise or blooming) consists in persisting in its beginning, which is demanded from the impossibility of the Origin’s relation to given being as position *extra nihilum* (Peiró 2020).

When the metaphysics of the gift raises the question of the actuality that grounds and sustains reality, the answer it achieves cannot be extramental existence along with nothingness as its assumed contrary, because in a philosophy of being, real being, because it is *ex nihilo*, lacks an absolute contrary. Only ideal being can be opposed to nothingness, because mental being or thought being can be conceived as a suppositum, that is to say, considering its previous position to existence. The consideration of the dynamics of real being, the *actus essendi*, cannot be made by thinking of an absolute opposition: being has no opposite because it is not ideal and cannot be presupposed as some sort of “absolute in-existence”. When talking about being as an act of existence, it is more adequate to talk about a radical distinction that, appealing to a transcendental leap, allows us to consider being as an act of existence without putting ourselves in a Parmenidean univocal position. The proper and radical distinction I suggest here is that between being *ex nihilo* and being as Origin. These acts are not opposite, then: they are diverse. That donated being is an *ex nihilo* reality means that its activity as a being that lacks consists in excluding nothingness from itself. The real activity is being, which as donated is equivalent to absolute beginning. Being *ex nihilo* is, as donated, beginning to be.

This is an idea worthy of consideration: the metaphysical development on what being *ex nihilo* is and means signals, according to Miguel García Valdecasas, finite being as threatened by the undefined nothingness that precedes it. This is a proper way to understand what is previous to it: the plenitude of the Origin of which created being is lacking. This anteriority, far from being temporal in nature, expresses atemporality as the donated nature of absolute beginning (García 2014, pp. 57–58). The founding giving action of reality is not a fact, or an event, but as actual today as in the first instant in which our universe began and the rest of the universes could begin to exist or will exist. Thus, the *donatio essendi* is as cognizable today as it was yesterday, it is “the clarity in which the beginning is lulled.” (García-Valdecasas 1998, pp. 93–94).

Understanding the gifted nature of being *ex nihilo* makes it possible to explain reality as something radically initiated and depending.¹⁸ Understanding the principal character of being becomes recognizing its gifted nature, speaking in absolute terms, because being as gifted is not what is constituted by God: it is that being, which conjoined with the essence, ends up as a concrete being. This is only possible if we overcome a substantial consideration of being and recognize being as gifted, that is to say, being as a principle, as an absolute inchoative and nonoriginary activity, which is more distinguishable from the Origin than from nothingness. This inchoative activity consists in its being a depending reference to the Giver.

These assertions lead us to consider how the metaphysics of the gift identify *ex parte creaturae* with it, for both its constitutive and constituted dimension bring together the existential nature of the principle of noncontradiction and the principle of causality. Being *ex nihilo* as gifted is equivalent to a being lacking itself, because the being of something does not refer to itself as it is not in reference to the essence (it distinguishes itself from it); distinct from its essence, the act of being of something is a noncontradictory activity. This is why being *ex nihilo* means beginning-to-be, an absolute or transcendental beginning, for, as Polo says, “beginning to be is non-contradictory insofar as it does not cease and is not followed, for if it were followed it would be followed by something different from being and would therefore cease to be.” (Polo 1991, p. 70). Being *ex nihilo* is a radical beginning that does not reach an end, it does not finalize or culminate, as all these would entail the ceasing of the noncontradictory activity, and hence its annihilation. As a transcendental inchoative activity, beginning-to-be means persisting in the beginning: being persistence. Persistence in the beginning means persisting in a noncontradictory activity (*esse ex nihil*), wherein resides the existential character of noncontradiction as an activity of being (Polo 2015a, pp. 148–49). Once again: persisting in the noncontradictory activity implies a being lacking itself, a being that does not refer to itself; and, if being *ex nihilo* does not refer to itself, it is because it is a reference to another, to the Original being, as being *ex Deo* (Vargas 2020, pp. 127–42).

The gifted nature of being *ex nihilo* entails its conjunction to the *donatio essendi*. In Thomistic terms, it is the equivalence within the actus essendi of the *positio extra nihilum* with the nature of lacking itself and dependence (Piá 1996, p. 937). Aquinas explains this in the first book of his Commentary to the Sentences, where he takes the meaning of nothingness in creation to distinguish divine generation from creation, insofar as, in the latter, lacking itself equals dependence on being.¹⁹ In this passage, Aquinas explains that if the expression “from nothingness” meant just a negation of the material cause, the Second Person of the Trinity would also be *ex nihilo*, and hence a creature, which is impossible. Moreover, being from nothingness is predicated on the affirmation of the order of posteriority to nothingness. In the real order, saying *extra nihilum* also entails saying extra contradiction, because for a creature, falling into contradiction is equivalent to falling into nothingness, which would happen if the persistence in the beginning ceased to be. As Aquinas defends in this text, in the real order, beyond what is merely logical, nothingness is nothing.²⁰

As we have seen, in being *ex nihilo*, dependence is an act: the act of dependence, which is the proper activity of the gifted actus essendi. The *donatio essendi* in being *ex nihilo* can be called relation insofar as the gifted being is not finished: there is unity in it but not identity. This is why the relation of dependence should be understood as an absolute reference of being *ex nihilo* to the Original being, not something added to it as an accident, and also why the reference of gifted being is not to its essence but to the divine being. The dependence of being *ex nihilo* is therefore one that is proper to that which cannot be consummated.

In sum, the point is to understand that in a metaphysics of being, being as first is equivalent to the existential character of the first principles. Which means, in Polo’s words, that there are different senses of the first. We can actually distinguish the principial nature of the first as a sense of the first. Thus, the donation of being as creature can be thought of as a beginning insofar as it principiates, i.e., as a radical novelty, because principiating is proper to what radically begins (Haya 1997, p. 193).

In the understanding of being as a principle, its meaning becomes different whether we refer it to divine being or to *ex nihilo*. Both meanings are ultimately irreducible: the principle, insofar as it principiates, is not, absolutely speaking, the principle as Origin, for as we have seen, it does not in any way originate or cause anything. Giving being is creating the beginning-to-be as a noncontradictory activity. Hence, donated being is not included or contained in God, nor does God make gifted being necessary in any way, because giving is not the same as causing (Haya 1997, p. 193). As we have said, creation as *donatio essendi* is free and gratuitous, and being *ex nihilo* is, as gifted activity, dependence.

Being as an absolute beginning is distinguished from God as an *ad extra* virtual relation. The positivity of gifted being lies here: in the authenticity of its positive actuality. The reason is that the notion of absolute beginning demands a positive distinction, one in which the distinction expressed by the expression *ad extra* becomes incomparably superior to the one expressed by *extra nihilum*. Giving being to gifted being means excluding nothingness from it, but the being that is gifted is, above all, the one that is radically distinct from the divine being. Giving being is not, then, giving being to “something” that has no being, nor is it giving the proper being of the One who is its own being. Giving being is giving a being to one that is not its own being: gifted being. From here, it is impossible not to think of gifted being as the dependent being, as absolute dependence is the notion that best shows the ontological status of the *ex nihilo* as distinct from the Origin. This is why Polo will say that “precisely because originated being depends, and dependence does not collapse the positivity out of the distinction, but rather explains it, originated being is an act of being.” (Polo 2016, p. 156).

As absolute beginning, being of itself is not an imperfection or a defect of the act of being of things: it is only being *ex nihilo*, i.e., gifted being. In the same way, absolute or absolute beginning or absolute dependence is not a description of any weakness of being, passivity or potentiality. The action of dependence is the highest activity realized

by the *ex nihilo actus essendi*; it is the way being lacks itself, or in other words, persists in noncontradictory actuality. Absolute dependence is what makes absolute beginning possible because its perfection as gifted being is dependence. Being is being, so to speak, because it is capable of dependence, so much so that if being is dependence, not-being is not-dependence. This is the last and fundamental metaphysical sense of nothingness: to stop existing would mean to stop depending, so that no-being for finite being is equivalent to not being *ex nihilo*, falling into contradiction, and ceasing as absolute beginning. This is not the annihilation of being but rather the wandering into nothingness, being without meaning that becomes existing without its constitutive lacking of itself, like how an astronaut that unhooked from their ship drifts eternally in the abyss.

The dynamic of gifted being and the elucidation of the act of being in donal terms makes the radical dependence of being *ex nihilo* regarding the absolute more radical, as well as more active, because its very being is dependence, that is, being a gift as beginning (Haya 1997, pp. 321–22). That is why the primary sense of dependence of gifted being cannot be achieved if it is understood in a passive way. On a first impression, the dependence inflicted by the undivinization of the universe understood as *donatio essendi* may seem to entail a certain passive character: dependence assumes something outside the dependent being, something passive. However, Polo holds that such an explanation is impossible in the creationist view, because absolute passivity would not be *extra nihilum*. If being gifted is by definition *extra nihilum*, the radical dependency that emerges from the notion of *donatio essendi* can only be an activity:

“The paradox of the (*donatio essendi*) is that its dependency is what constitutes (being *ex nihilo*) insofar as it is an activity, insofar as it is an act, because as its dependency is absolute, it is equivalent to its keeping in existence, not being ultimately constituted, or sufficiently. Creating is not producing something that is already enough, because the dependency would then be broken. Creation has to be something continuous and instantaneous. The demand for a continuation (to being) does not impact God: it is a demand for the creature. Every neediness of (being *ex nihilo*) is, in this fashion, activity: the creation demands to be ‘kept in existence’, which is precisely its *energeia* or activity. Thus, God is also given the name Primary Activity or Pure Act.” (Polo 1993, pp. 134–35)

Thus, explaining the reality of finite being means to recognize that it is a real activity as being *ex nihilo*, a being whose activity—existence—consists in lacking itself and excludes nothingness from itself, which is in turn equivalent to absolute beginning. As an act of being, being *ex nihilo* means beginning-to-be-in-dependence. This is its proper ontological dynamic as an act of existence.

5. Conclusions

From our previous considerations we may conclude the following:

1. Metaphysical nihilism can only be overcome when philosophy welcomes an understanding of finite being that, as *ex nihilo*, excludes nothingness. In order to do so, we can face the question of the existence of reality and its own actuality based on the metaphysics of the gift. In the first place, the origination of being *ex nihilo* as *donatio essendi*, and then towards a reflection on finite being as given and absolute beginning.
2. The origin of the finite being should be described as absolute donation. The reason is that it allows us to think of finite being as radical novelty and absolute benefit, with no trace of passivity, ambiguity, or ontological nihilism. In the *donatio essendi*, the gifted being is in no way existent prior to the given. The nature of giving implies producing or doing what is given, i.e., giving what the given is not previously. In an absolute donation, the gift is “generated” as it is given; being as absolute donation means being-given. The notion of absolute gift through *donatio essendi* is inseparable from the character of given, a character that defines and determines it. That is why the metaphysics of the gift is so appropriate to determine the ontological character of being *ex nihilo* as absolute *acceptio esse*.

3. The real communication of being as *donatio essendi* allows us to consider its radicality through its gratuitousness and freedom. Thus, the origination of finite beings is real communication because it is a real and absolute donation. The very notion of *donatio essendi* permits the safekeeping of divine freedom because communicating being *ex nihilo* does not imply a real *ad extra* relation in God. Consequently, the absolute gratuitousness of creation becomes an absolute benefit.
4. The idea of *donatio essendi* points to the *ex nihilo* giving of an existence whose perfection is set in its reference to Another, in giving itself. This is the plenitude of the gifted being. As gifted, being *ex nihilo* is not static, but intrinsically temporal, insofar as gifted being is temporal, because giving being is not limited (on God's part) to "placing" being. It is donating the gift, or rather, donating the giving.
5. The existential value of the principle of noncontradiction is the persistence in noncontradictory activity, which means that we should reject any meaning of possible activity to just affirm the equivalence of being *ex nihilo* and noncontradiction as activity, precisely in terms of its gifted nature. This implies the rejection of a real equivalence, according to the principle of noncontradiction, between being and nothingness. The idea of existence as "opposed to" nothingness or "non-existence" should also be disregarded, insofar as it is an opposition of reason. On the contrary, the principle of noncontradiction, as real extramental principle, is the noncontradictory existence, i.e., being *ex nihilo*.
6. The donated act is diverse and not opposite to the Original being. It is in this sense that we claim that being *ex nihilo* is first, and that is why its activity should be understood as beginning, which entails its radical novelty: being *ex nihilo*, as *position extra nihilum*, is a form of existence that premieres as beginning. A being that begins is "first" not in the sense of originary, but as absolute beginning, because nothing precedes or follows being *ex nihilo*. It cannot be compared with anything that exists like it does, as it is secondary to nothing (it is *extra nihilum*, not *extra causam*).
7. Being *ex nihilo* is not the kind of being whose activity resolves in becoming free of nothingness in order to continue being. Being *ex nihilo*, rather, means distinguishing itself radically from nothingness; on the other hand, it is *extra nihilum* only insofar as it is *ad extra* regarding God. In other words, as nothingness is nothing, being *ex nihilo* consists in getting rid of nothingness by differentiating itself from it, which in a positive sense means being donated by an absolute giving (*donatio essendi*). The *ad extra* existence of the *donatio essendi* should therefore be understood as a distinction, not exteriority. This distinction excludes all comparisons: it is no determination or category of gifted being that allows for a comparison with the Giver, with which he is not linked in any causal or relational sense. For gifted being, its existence is not a proper determination that is previous to being gifted, and hence comparable to the Being that is its own being, but rather its reality as lacking its own being, which points towards its determination as being-given (this is what its gifted nature means).
8. The activity of being *ex nihilo* as gifted is not centered in rejecting nothingness but in being-dependent-beginning, i.e., transcendental beginning and absolute dependency on its Origin. This is the proper activity of finite being, characterized here by the principles of noncontradiction and causality. Being *ex nihilo* is absolute beginning and dependence, which is the way in which a finite being is dependent, as donated by an absolute donation. Being as beginning is being received as gifted, not as caused or produced, and therefore being towards and for another: an existence that refers to another.
9. The *donatio essendi* is an absolute reception of being (*esse*), as Aquinas claims, and that reception grounds its being an absolute reference and dependence to the Giver. Being subsistent as an absolute gift: this means being an absolute donation. A personal being becomes an absolute donation by accepting and destinating itself, which is its own activity as gifted personal being. This makes it *ex Deo* rather than *ex nihilo*: it distinguishes itself more from the Creator than from nothingness (as, properly

speaking, nothingness does not actually exist). As *ex Deo*, personal gifted being has a natural order with regards to nothingness, which determines it as a dependent being, but its personal nature allows for an increase in its donating activity in receiving its own being as its acceptance and donating itself through destinating itself. Its plenitude lies here.

10. Through the metaphysics of the gift, a metaphysical understanding of reality can actually acquire the full positivity that is proper to being, one which was lost throughout the history of philosophy. As such, *donatio essendi* is the theme of the absolute communication and coexistence of two different kinds of being: Original being and originated being. The principality of originated being rests in its novelty, and beginning being *ex nihilo* should therefore be characterized, above all, by centering our attention on these two parameters, as beginning and as novelty. Only then, without assuming anything about being, can metaphysics take a step forward to hold that the absence of anything previous explains what being lacks: no thing is its own existence. This lacking, its real distinction, manifests that being, for each thing, is its reference, that is, its dependence. Novelty and dependence are, therefore, the two attributes that define the nature of the gifted character of existence, in its utmost comprehension.

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Notes

- ¹ This crisis is not only experienced within the realm of experimental and human sciences, nor is it only an ethical crisis—whether collectively or individually understood—but rather a personal crisis of meaning. Moreover, we must assert that human beings are in a state of constant tension, of permanent crisis, which has to do, among other reasons, with the fact that the spiritual condition of man translates into a capacity for unyielding, limitless growth. The possibility for growth—and lessening—of man manifests our condition of the proper and constitutive crisis of human beings. See (Vargas 2017; Zorroza 2019).
- ² It is important to point out that the crisis Husserl refers to is not one of science itself regarding its capacity to attain its objects through its proper method (whether it is a physical science or a science of mind): “The scientific rigor of all these disciplines, the convincingness of their theoretical accomplishments, and their enduringly compelling successes are unquestionable” (Husserl 1976); A similar idea may be found in (Zubiri 1994, pp. 27–57).
- ³ “At any rate, the contrast between the “scientific” character of this group of sciences and the “unscientific” character of philosophy is unmistakable” (Husserl 1976, *The Crisis*, cit., pp. 4–5).
- ⁴ Derrida will suggest the necessity of moving beyond Heidegger’s failed deconstruction of metaphysics towards one of language itself, as its structure secures the very origin of metaphysics. It is, however, a deconstruction more rightly understood as de-sedimentation rather than demolition. See (Derrida 1967, pp. 21–24); see also (Inciarte and Llano 2007, pp. 28, 121–31). Regarding radical Hermeneutics, cf. (Miguel 2010, pp. 55–75); and (Gadamer 1975).
- ⁵ In Aquinas’ ontology, the principle of a creature, the *proprium esse* of each thing, turns every being into a perfection insofar as it makes it be so; that is to say, the proper *esse* of a being is the perfection of such a being, and not just one among many other constituents. Cf. S. Th., I, q. 4, a. 1, ad 3. Cfr. S. Th., I, q. 3, a. 4; In Sent., I, d. 8, q. 1, a. 1. In this respect, Alejandro Llano properly holds that “the act of being is the immanent origin of the plenitude of each being according to its proper essence. That is why the nobility of each thing arouses from its being. When Thomas Aquinas repeatedly holds that the *esse* of each thing is its perfection, he is not just pointing out—as a limited sense of ‘perfectio’ might suggest—that it is limit, the definitive realization of something that is coming-to-be. In a metaphysical sense, ‘perfectio’ means positivity, goodness, plenitude, value, in their most radical meaning.” (Llano 1984, p. 295). Regarding the intelligible nature of reality according to Thomistic metaphysics, see (Ramos 2014, pp. 95–111).
- ⁶ Indeed, if finite being is necessarily *ex nihilo*, we can establish the classic problems of being in what Zubir rightly calls the “horizon of nihilism”. Zubiri himself traces his *About the Problem of Philosophy* around this plan, dedicating its fifth chapter to “the horizon of Western philosophy: creation and nihilism” (Zubiri 1996, pp. 3 y 30).
- ⁷ Regarding what I call the “metaphysics of the gift”, see Fernando Haya’s (1997) extraordinary.
- ⁸ This quotation is taken from (Inciarte and Llano 2007, p. 349); it translates an expression from Husserl, E., *Vorgegeben Welt, Historizität, Trieb, Instinkt* (Ms. 1934, Sign. E III 10, p. 18), y citado por S. Strasser, “Das Gottesproblem in der Spätphilosophie Edmund Husserls”, *Philosophisches Jahrbuch*, 67 (1958), p. 142.

- ⁹ Our task becomes, then, a metaphysical understanding; in Zubiri's words, "creation is now, in the concrete, an 'origination of being' (. . .), a radical origin from what is not being, from nothingness. Being is always not-nothingness, it is *creatio ex nihilo*" (Zubiri 1996, op. cit., p. 47).
- ¹⁰ S. Th., I, q. 28, a. 1, ad 3; see also *De causis*, lect. XI. Translations of the Summa theologiae are taken from the 1920 edition by the Fathers of the English Dominican Province, available online at www.newadvent.org/summa (accessed on 6 May 2020) (ed. Kevin Knight).
- ¹¹ In the same line of the metaphysics of the gift, Angel Luis González claims that "the highest sense of being is precisely gifting" (González 2013, p. 49). Indeed, as pointed out by Haya and Gonzalez, personal being has more to do with giving than with that which is given: what is given, gifts, belong to the essence, while being is giving. The origin of this metaphysical view is in Leonardo Polo, who, in his study *Having and gifting (Tener y dar)*, suggests that a human person is not only nor specifically defined as a being capable of having, but rather he is personal because, while endorsing having, he is capable of gifting. That is why, against the question of what lies beyond our tendency to possess and possession itself, Polo answers the following: "Obviously, donation. If the activity of the Will is donating, it transcends what the Greeks understood as *télos*: this is a Christian hyperteology. Gifting is giving without losing, an activity that is above a balance of wins and loses, winning without acquiring or acquiring while giving" (Polo 2015c, pp. 229–30). Thus, the personal created being consists in gifting: gifting gifts, not gifting itself, for gifting as such belongs exclusively to God, as only he can donate existence, which cannot be confused with the given (the essence).
- ¹² "Creare autem est dare esse"; In Sent., I, d. 37, q. 1, a. 1, sol. Cfr. In Sent., I, d. 7, q. 1, a. 1, ad 3; In Sent., II, d. 1, q. 1, a. 2, ad 2; S. Th., I, q. 9, a. 2, sol.; q. 104, a. 1, ad 4. In line with these considerations, I hold that any investigation into the meaning of creation as gifting demands that our metaphysical viewpoint is extended to anthropology, as gifting is a free action that is proper to personal beings, and the only accessible freedom to our natural understanding is the one of the personal human being. In the same way, Trinitarian theology itself makes use of our analysis of the personal created being, only then being able to analogously consider divine personal relations.
- ¹³ See (de Aquino 2005b, *Super Io.*, cap. 1, l. 5, n. 133). Polo comments that "when Aquinas says *creatio est donatio essendi*, he is no longer regarding being in the order of grounding; he augments the causal view. When you gift something, you are not grounding; gifting goes beyond grounding. That is to say: being is; it is not caused or made, but rather given. Which is more proper of creation: making being or gifting being? (. . .) Gifting, insofar as gifted, is in the order of coexistence." (Polo 1993, p. 175).
- ¹⁴ Regarding human freedom in Aquinas' thought, cfr. (Peiró and Zorroza 2014, pp. 435–49).
- ¹⁵ Cfr. De Pot., q. 3, a. 4, sol.; C. G., II, cap. 15.
- ¹⁶ "Creatio active significat actionem divinam, quae est eius essentia cum relatione ad creaturam"; S. Th., I, q. 45, a. 3, ad 1, but this is a relation of reason.
- ¹⁷ We should note that a metaphysics of totality allows no intensification: it is a closed system that depends on making explicit what is already implicitly present. Cfr. (Haya 1997, op. cit., p. 315). The intensification of being, on the other hand, is always inside a finite order, for the domain of donated being can be a greater and better remission to the Origin (never in identifying with it). The perfection of gifted being does not consist in it stopping being donated, nor in its falling into nothingness, nor in the sense that its perfection lies in "divinizing" itself, so as to be confused with divine being. To the metaphysical view of creation as *donatio essendi*, against Hegelian dialectics, the overcoming of the limitations of created being, as distinct to the divine being, cannot be solved in the confusion of the created and the divine, but rather in intensifying its own being created qua created, which implies a greater sharpness in its distinction from uncreated being. For a creature, "being more" means to be a better creature.
- ¹⁸ We could say that being finite as donated and dependence is what Aquinas calls being by participation. The Thomistic doctrine of participation in being, one of whose manifestations is the real distinction between being and essence, sets the real state of the creature in the metaphysical consideration of the real composition of beings. It is through the real distinction that Aquinas achieves an explanation for the authenticity of the created being as an act by participation without its dissolution in the divine Being. Only God is its own Being; in everything else, being differs from the essence. Cfr. S. Th. I, q. 61, a. 1, sol.
- ¹⁹ Cfr. In Sent., I, d. 5, q. 2, a. 2, sol. Cfr. S. Th., I, q. 45, a. 1, ad 3; q. 46, a. 2, ad 2; In Sent., II, d. 1, q. 1, a. 2, sol.
- ²⁰ In the realm of reason, the principle of noncontradiction is a certain prelude to the idea of nothingness, which is a being of reason. In reality, however, nothingness should be understood as "to cease" or "being followed" by absolute beginning. Not ceasing points directly to the Origin insofar as in beings; the act of being is really distinct from the essence and, because it is caused, can be investigated without mentally determining it or making it dependent on the essence. This ultimately means that, for created beings, the lacking of themselves and the nature of dependence are intrinsically linked. In other words, radical beginning shows radical dependence, because persisting in beginning is impossible without radical dependence. Cfr. (Polo 2015b, op. cit., p. 207).

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